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Determination of Acetone in Aqueous Solution

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ACETONE in aqueous solution has been determined with various but unsatisfactory chromogens^{1,2}, since they resort to rigorous conditions for the quantitative determination of acetone. Under suitable conditions, acetone has been found to react sensitively and selectively with diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid to give a purple colour, which is stable in the presence of starch.

Experimental

The 1.5% diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid solution was prepared as described elsewhere³. The 200 ppm acetone solution was prepared in distilled water. The absorption measurements were made with a Shimadzu UV-210 A double-beam spectrophotometer and Baush & Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. Sodium hydroxide (35%) and starch (0.05%) solutions were prepared in distilled water.

Procedure: To an aliquot of sample solution (10-180 μg of acetone) in a 20 ml volumetric flask, were added reagent solution (2 ml), sodium hydroxide solution (2 ml), starch solution (2 ml) and distilled water to the mark. After 25 min, the absorbance of the purple coloured solution was measured against the reagent blank, within another 15 min, at 530 nm using 1 cm cells. The amount of acetone was deduced from the calibration curve prepared from 10-180 μg of acetone.

Results and Discussion

Colour reaction and absorption spectrum: In alkaline medium, α -hydrogen containing compounds couple with diazonium salts to produce coloured chromophores³⁻⁵. This forms the basis of the method. When dilute solution of acetone and diazotised *p*-aminobenzoic acid reagent are mixed in the presence of alkali, a purple coloured compound formed which has an absorbance maximum at 530 nm. This wavelength is adopted in all subsequent experiments.

Effect of starch: The purple colour decays upon dilution with water. To overcome such difficulty, reducing agents and protective colloids were tried. Reducing agents are unsatisfactory since they changed the purple colour to a less intense yellow. Of the surfactant tested, 2 ml of 0.05% starch solution, when introduced after all other reagents and before dilution to the mark, is found to stabilise the colour for 15 min after 25 min development period. The amount of reagent and sodium hydroxide were of 2 ml each.

Under the above conditions, Beer's law adheres to solutions containing up to 180 μg of acetone per 20 ml, with a molar absorptivity of $6.2 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The accuracy of this method (range 10-180 μg of acetone) is found to be +4.1 to +0.31 with a corresponding standard deviation percent of 6.62-1.01 (five determinations). The interfering effect of some foreign compounds was studied, and their tolerable amounts (ppm) in the presence of 5 ppm acetone, are: acetaldehyde (2), acetoacetic acid (20), amyl alcohol (15), aniline (85), benzaldehyde (60), chloroform (65), cyclohexanone (15), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (13), dioxan (40), ethanol (15), ethyl acetate (55), ethyl acetoacetate (12), formaldehyde (70), formic acid (50), lactic acid (25), methanol (50) and propanol (20). These figures correspond to the amount of foreign compounds causing an error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance reading.

The present method is simple, rapid, sensitive and selective. It is more simple than the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and the salicylaldehyde methods and also, more sensitive than the former.

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